

Kinetics of Vanadium(V) Oxidation of Acetone and Chloroacetone

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The oxidation of acetone and chloroacetone by vanadium(V) reaction is first order in vanadium(V) and ketone and second order in H^+ . Kinetic evidence for the formation of a complex of vanadium(V) and ketone is obtained. A probable mechanism with vanadium(V) acting as one electron oxidant, involving C-H bond fission in the slow step via free radical formation has been suggested.

THE oxidation of aliphatic ketones involves reaction commonly at α -position¹. Several oxidants, like alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ion², potassium permanganate³, cerium (IV)⁴ and manganese(II)⁵ have been used for the oxidation of acetone. Gaudfroy⁶ studied the oxidation of acetone by vanadium(V) analytically. The motivation of the present study is to arrive at a probable mechanism for the oxidation of acetone and chloroacetone by vanadium(V) in sulphuric acid on the basis of kinetic results.

Experimental

Vanadium(V) solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate (Riedel) in appropriate concentration of sulphuric acid (A.R., B.D.H.). Acetone (A.R., B.D.H.) and chloroacetone (Sisco) were distilled and their aqueous solution was used. Other chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H., or of standard grade.

The reactant solutions were allowed to attain the desired temperature by keeping them in a thermostat ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) and progress of the reaction was followed at regular intervals by estimating the unconsumed vanadium(V) with standard solution of Mohr's salt using *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

Under the condition of kinetic run acetic and formic acids were identified as the final products in the oxidation of acetone⁷. The stoichiometry was determined after keeping the reaction mixture ($[Ketone] \gg [V^V]$) for several days. The number of moles of V^V consumed per mole of ketone was found to be 6.

The oxidation proceeds through the formation of free radicals as intermediate which was confirmed by induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile monomer.

Kinetic studies were performed by taking acetone, chloroacetone and sulphuric acid $\gg V^V$ at constant ionic strength. Pseudo first order rate constants on eight-fold variation of oxidant concentration, have shown that the rate of disappearance of V^V followed the first order kinetics uniformly (Tables 1 and 2). Plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time showed a linear straight line in each kinetic run for both the ketones, indicating first order dependence in oxidant. However, the values of second order rate constant (k_2) obtained at different initial concentrations of substrate have shown a constant value suggesting that the reaction is also of first order with respect to the substrate. Further, the plot of k_1^{-1} vs $[ketone]^{-1}$ shows an intercept on Y axis indicating complex formation of oxidant and ketones.

TABLE 1 - DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON REACTANTS AT 45°

$10^2[V^V]$ M	[Acetone] M	$[H^+]$ M	μ M	10^3k_1 min ⁻¹	k_2
1.0	8.0	6.0	6.10	9.82	—
2.0	8.0	6.0	6.10	10.82	—
4.0	8.0	6.0	6.10	11.43	1.43
6.0	8.0	6.0	6.10	11.51	—
8.0	8.0	6.0	6.10	11.45	—
4.0	2.0	6.0	6.10	2.83	1.41
4.0	3.0	6.0	6.10	4.40	1.46
4.0	5.0	6.0	6.10	7.08	1.41
4.0	7.0	6.0	6.10	9.73	1.39
4.0	10.0	6.0	6.10	14.10	1.41
4.0	8.0	4.5	6.65	6.51	3.21*
4.0	8.0	5.0	6.65	8.45	3.38*
4.0	8.0	5.5	6.65	10.31	3.40*
4.0	8.0	6.0	6.65	12.05	3.34*
4.0	8.0	6.5	6.65	13.98	3.30*

$$10^3k_2 = 1/[Acetone], 1 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{min}^{-1}$$

$$* 10^3k_2 = 1/[H^+], 1^2 \text{ mol}^{-2}\text{min}^{-1}$$

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON REACTANTS AT 40°

10 ² [V ^v] M	[CA] M	[H ⁺] M	μ M	10 ² k ₁ min ⁻¹	k ₂
1.0	8.0	5.0	5.10	13.15	—
2.0	8.0	5.0	5.10	13.09	—
3.0	8.0	5.0	5.10	13.66	—
4.0	8.0	5.0	5.10	13.41	1.68
6.0	8.0	5.0	5.10	14.01	—
4.0	2.0	5.0	5.10	3.26	1.63
4.0	3.0	5.0	5.10	4.84	1.61
4.0	5.0	5.0	5.10	8.62	1.72
4.0	7.0	5.0	5.10	11.69	1.67
4.0	8.0	4.5	6.05	11.13	5.49*
4.0	8.0	5.0	6.05	14.19	5.67*
4.0	8.0	5.5	6.05	16.52	5.46*
4.0	8.0	6.0	6.05	20.52	5.70*

CA = Chloroacetone.

10 k₂ = 1/[Chloroacetone], l mol⁻¹ min⁻¹

* 10³k₂ = 1/[H⁺]², l² mol⁻² min⁻¹

The effect of varying [H⁺] at constant ionic strength exhibits a linear increase in the pseudo first order rate constant (Tables 1 and 2). The values of k₂ (k₂ = k₁/[H⁺]²) were obtained constant for both the ketones. Also, the plot of k₁ vs [H⁺]² gave a slope of 1.81 and 2.12 for acetone and chloroacetone, respectively confirming that the rate of disappearance with H⁺ is two. Since no positive intercept was obtained, it may be concluded that the reactions involve acid independent path. Hammett plot between log k₁ and H₀ gave a slope of 0.45 and 0.48 for acetone and chloroacetone respectively. Mehrotra⁸ and Chithambarathanu *et al.*⁹, have also reported similar observations in the oxidation of citric acid and methyl ethyl ketone by V^v.

Addition of NaHSO₄ at constant [H⁺] showed an increase in the pseudo first order rate constant in case of both the ketones. For example, for [HSO₄⁻] = 6.0 M and under the conditions [V^v] = 4.0 × 10⁻² M, [Acetone] = 0.8 M, [H⁺] = 6.0 M and temp. = 45°, k₁ = 12.84 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹, while at [HSO₄⁻] = 8.0 M, k₁ = 21.62 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹. The plot of k₁ vs [HSO₄⁻]² shows linearity with a positive intercept.

It has been observed that pseudo first order rate constant increases inversely with the dielectric constant of the medium. For example, in 10% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid and under the conditions [V^v] = 4.0 × 10⁻² M, [Acetone] = 0.8 M, [H⁺] = 6.0 M, μ = 6.3 and temp. = 45°, k₁ = 14.03 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹, while in 40% aqueous acetic acid k₁ = 18.46 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹.

Kinetic runs have been carried out at different temperatures (45°-60°). The values of various activation parameters have been obtained from the Arrhenius plot (Table 3).

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹	A sec ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.
Acetone	17.59 ± 0.48	2.22 × 10 ⁸ ± 0.158	-20.73 ± 1.2
Chloroacetone	8.36 ± 0.39	1.64 × 10 ⁸ ± 0.3	-43.92 ± 0.1

Mechanism :

That the reaction involves the keto form of the substrates is favoured by the fact that it follows first order disappearance strictly even at high concentration⁹⁻¹¹. A second order dependence in acid (>4.5 M) and HSO₄⁻ clearly suggests that the V(OH)₂ (HSO₄)₂⁺ species⁸ of V^v is involved in the reaction. This species combines with the ketones and form complex. In the rate determining step the complex dissociates with C-H fission to yield free radical by H⁺ abstraction. The rate steps may be written as,

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{Complex}] \quad (6)$$

$$= k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{Ketone}] [H^+]^2 [HSO_4^-]^2 [VO_2^+] \quad (7)$$

Substituting for [V^v]_T and [VO₂⁺],

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{Ketone}] [H^+]^2 [HSO_4^-]^2}{1 + K_1 [H^+]^2 [HSO_4^-]^2 + K_1 K_2 [\text{Ketone}] [H^+]^2 [HSO_4^-]^2} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{[\text{Ketone}]} \left[\frac{1}{k_1 K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2 [HSO_4^-]^2} + \frac{1}{k_1 K_2} \right] + \frac{1}{k_1} \quad (9)$$

A plot of 1/k_{obs} vs 1/[Ketone] is obtained as a straight line with a positive slope.

Assuming that K₁ << K₁K₂, equation (8), may be written as,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{Ketone}] [H^+]^2 [HSO_4^-]^2$$

At constant [H₂SO₄],

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k' [\text{Ketone}], \text{ where } k' = k_1 K_1 K_2 [H^+]^2 [HSO_4^-]^2$$

Thus, the proposed mechanism can account for the experimental results. The faster rate of oxidation of chloroacetone than acetone is attributed to the presence of a strong electronegative group in the former which facilitates the oxidation.

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PANDEY, SHARMA & SHARMA : KINETICS OF VANADIUM(V) OXIDATION ETC.

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